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**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>**Research Article****EFFECTIVE ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT AND
INVESTMENT AS THE WAYS OF OVERCOMING THE CRISIS
OF ECOLOGICAL AND ECONOMIC SYSTEMS****Vladimir Anatolievich Rubtzov^{1*}, Mikhail Viktorovich Rozhko¹, Niyaz Kamilevich
Gabdrakhmanov¹**¹Kazan Federal University, Institute of Management, Economics and Finance, Kazan Federal University, 18 Kremlyovskaya street Kazan 420008, Russian Federation, Russia**Abstract:**

An abnormal load on the territory, exceedance the limits of environmental sustainability, unfavorable ecological situation lead to the degradation of the region. Taking into account the interaction of the economy and the environment, catastrophic consequences can be avoided. The region, investing in modernization of its economy, in terms of improving environmental safety, becomes attractive for investment.

Keywords: *ecological and economic systems, territorial development, environmental management, investment, natural environment.*

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INTRODUCTION:

In Russia, there is a large-scale economic transformation, which negatively affects the country's ecological appearance - the dominance of energy and material-intensive industries, determining the high anthropogenic load on the nature, the underdevelopment of resource-saving technologies, the consumer attitude to nature during the "initial accumulation of capital", the residual principle of financing of environmental problems and many other things.

The unfolding situation of interaction between the nature and society creates a real threat of formation on the vast space of "critical" socio-ecological and economic systems, which are complex territorial entities, where the economic and environmental loads exceed some reasonable limits [5]. For any region, an abnormal load on the territory, exceedance the limits of environmental sustainability will ultimately result in serious consequences [6, 10]. Unfavorable ecological situation will deplorably affect social aspects, in particular, the quality of population life. In turn, a decrease in the quality of population life, excess incidence will lead to unpleasant demographic consequences. All this will affect the economy - growth, built without consideration of environmental requirements, can result in economic problems [7]. The region may become recessionary.

METHOD:

Taking into account the relationship between the economy and the environment, catastrophic consequences can be avoided and even additional benefits can be obtained. The region, investing in the development of environmentally-friendly and environmentally-clean manufacturing, will have serious competitive advantages in the future. Investments should be spent for implementation of innovations to achieve the best balance in the system "economy - ecology" (maximum economic efficiency with minimum environmental load).

From the point of view of improving environmental safety, the region, investing in modernization of its economy, becomes an investment-attractive [8]. With the transition of such region to the postindustrial stage of development, a favorable ecological situation will become one of the main competitive advantages [1].

RESULTS:

The main tendency of modern environmental management is the following: the rates of decrease in production is much faster than the rate of reduction of its impact on the natural environment. Over the past

decades, there have been significant changes in the role of particular economic regions in the economy of the Russian Federation. The Center and the North Caucasus have sharply lost their positions in the industry of Russia. Against this background, the relative importance of the Volga region, the Urals, the regions of Western Siberia and the North is growing. Paradoxically, the agricultural importance of the northern and eastern regions is also increasing.

Thus, material production, and consequently, economic loads on nature have relatively moved to the "East" of the country.

The economic load on landscapes was especially noticeable in the Central and the North Caucasus economic regions. There is every reason to suppose that in the near future such tendencies will continue. This is evidenced by the analysis of the distribution of area investment, which are, in fact, future anthropogenic loads. So, over the past 10 years, 50 - 60% of industrial fixed capital expenditures were accounted for the Urals, the Volga region, and the region of Western Siberia [2].

The interest of investors is focused on the industrialized regions, localized in the European part of Russia, including Moscow and the Moscow region, St. Petersburg and the Leningrad region, the Kaliningrad region, the Rostov region, and the regions of the Urals - Sverdlovsk and Chelyabinsk regions. As for our region - the Republic of Tatarstan, according to the rating of Russian regions, in terms of investment attractiveness and investment potential, it takes the second place after Moscow. According to Mirzoyan T.S. [3], such a high rating is also confirmed by the fact, that a few years ago only 5 territorial entities of Russia had special legislation on foreign investment, including our republic.

On the other hand, in solving the urgent problems of the "recessionary" ecological and economic regions, there is another way out. So, the development of these regions can be presented from the standpoint of the effectiveness of environmental management as the main result of social and production activity [4, 9].

The effectiveness of environmental management is made by work efforts in the territory of this region, by recycling regional reserves of natural resources and raw materials into economically significant attractive utilities or market goods. It expresses the ratio of the results of activity R , and the costs of achieving them C , expressed in comparable units: $U = R/C$. Consequently, the efficiency is a dimensionless value, i.e. the number, showing how

many times the return of resources cost unit will increase, as a result of their rational use.

The processes of regional activity are known to be represented by three production sectors: mining, manufacturing, trade and services, including banking. Industry preferences for the development of regional activities are determined, firstly, by the historical and geographical conditions of the ratio "population-territory-resources-economy" and, secondly, by the requirements of the country's economic development. In each region, respectively, the production processes of all three branches take place.

The analysis of data for 2000 - 2006 found the industrial migration of regions in the direction of the greatest preferences. So, there was a migration of subjects of the Russian Federation with heavy and low-paid production conditions (extractive and processing industries with low-efficiency raw materials technologies) into more comfortable and highly paid industries (trade and services, including financial ones) (for example, the Republic of Tatarstan, Rostov, Samara and Nizhny Novgorod regions in 2003 - 2005).

In the conditions of the financial crisis of 2008-2009 the regional environmental management of Russia developed in three directions: 1) "production" - anti-crisis development from self-sacrificing labor to harmony of production interests; 2) "eco-development" - anti-crisis development to environmentally oriented projects; 3) "accumulation" - excessive accumulation of money for the subsequent removal of them from the social and production spheres.

Kochurov B.I. and Smirnov V.A. [4] define three types of regions, according to the challenges of the financial crisis: 1) regions of the least risk of the crisis - financial flows equally ensure national interests (highly efficient use of natural resources and interests of personal enrichment (gaining of earned profit)); 2) regions - potential generators of the financial crisis - financial flows ensure mainly interests of personal enrichment at the expense of oppression of national interests and 3) regions, experiencing the consequences of the financial crisis - a monetary deficit, impoverished financial flows ensure the production processes, that have withstood crisis.

CONCLUSIONS:

Thus, unique conditions have been created for the development of an important national innovation - eco-territories, that allows, firstly, to redistribute highly anthropogenous loads among Russian regions and to improve the ecological situation there, and secondly, to rely on the own natural and resource potential of the region.

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